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**Infertility as a Major Contributory Factor to Marital Disharmony among Couples of Ogoni
Ethnic Nationality in Rivers State, Nigeria**

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Abstract

The study evaluated the emotional reactions of couples from selected communities in Ogoni ethnic nationality. This was a descriptive study in which 500 infertile couples were selected by convenience sampling and were evaluated. 27.8% couples developed some form of marital disharmony whereas 56.2% couples' marital harmony was not affected. With regard to sexuality, only 27.8% of the couples could maintain better sexual performance, while 16.8% of the couples found no change in their sex life. Emotional reactions experienced were: shock in women (29.0%) and in men (27.2%), depression in women (31.8%) and in men (22.8%) and 14% of the men were found to show more negative interacting with the infertile wives and threat of divorce ensued to 10% females. Around 57.4% of instances of males were sympathetic. Sense of guilt and self-blame developed in 29.0% of males and 30.60% of the females. Male infertility level 80.2%, while the female was 97%. This study illuminated the emotional reactions of infertile couples. Infertile couples had high negative feelings, low self-esteem, poor social support, less freedom and less number of opportunities.

Keywords: infertility, couples, females, males, psychological, pregnancy